

GENETIC ALGORITHM FOR LEAKAGE REDUCTION THROUGH IVC USING VERILOG

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ABSTRACT:

VLSI design constraints are always area, power and delay. Power consumption of VLSI has become a leading design concern with the growth of complexity and density. Leakage power reduces battery life for the entire portable battery operated device such as mobile phones, laptop and camcorder and so on. Reduction of leakage power is of peak concern in the present trend of nanotechnology. Many techniques have been projected to reduce the leakage power consumption, but most of these approaches require the process technology support. Input Vector Control is one of the approaches used for static power reduction in standby mode. Leakage in a circuit depends on input vector applied at primary inputs due to stack effect. Minimum leakage vector is the input vector to which a circuit can suggest a minimum leakage for a certain set of test patterns. This paper presents Minimum Leakage Vector for various test circuits using genetic algorithm. The algorithm is simulated in Verilog HDL to acquire MLV. Results explore that heuristic approaches can be considered as better algorithms in finding optimum solution. Another improvement begins during simulation is that implementation of algorithm in HDL converges in lesser number of iterations with runtime savings compared to random search method.

Keywords:

Leakage Power, Genetic Algorithm, Input Vector Control, Minimum Leakage Vector, Verilog HDL implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the VLSI technology and supply/threshold voltage maintain scaling down, leakage power has develop into more and most important in the power dissipation of today's CMOS circuits. For example, it is proposed that sub- threshold leakage power can supply as much as 42% of the total power in the 90 nm process generation [5]. Many techniques thus have been projected recently to reduce the leakage power consumption. Dual threshold voltage process use devices with higher threshold voltage along non-critical paths to decrease leakage current while maintaining the performance [2].

Multiple-threshold CMOS (MTCMOS) technique places a high V_{th} device in sequence with low V_{th} circuitry, creating a sleep transistor [4]. Calhoun et al. proposed a methodology to comprise sleep transistors in MTCMOS [8]. In dynamic threshold MOS (DTMOS) [5], the gate and body are coupled

together and the threshold voltage is changed dynamically to suit the operating state of the circuit. Another technique to dynamically regulate threshold voltages is the variable threshold CMOS(VTCMOS) [9]. Controlling the body bias voltage to reduce leakage is discussed in [8]. All of these approaches require the process technology support. Scaling down the technology to nanometer, results in the increase of sub threshold leakage current exponentially with the reduction of supply voltage(V_{dd}) and threshold voltage. Sub threshold leakage current dominates other leakage current components in current CMOS technologies. Minimizing leakage power in portable devices is the major task to extend the battery life, as most of the time, portable devices operate in standby mode. Minimizing leakage power in portable devices is the major task to extend the battery life, as most of the time, portable devices operate in standby mode.

IVC is a popular approach used for leakage power reduction. IVC is preferred over other approaches as it is independent of process technology parameters. IVC is based on transistor stacking effect. This technique involves parking a circuit in minimum leakage state with no performance over head. Minimum leakage vector (MLV) is the minimum leakage state among set of test inputs. This MLV can be forced in to test circuit using multiplexers (with sleep signal used as a select signal for the MUX)[7]. Sub threshold

Fig.1. Two Input NAND Gate

and gate oxide leakage currents varies with the input vector applied to the CMOS gate[2].

Figure.1 shows two input NAND gate. Due to stacking effect of transistors in NAND gate leakage current depends on input vector [7]. This leakage depends on number of off transistors connected in the stack. Table.1 shows leakage currents for all possible input combinations of a two input NAND gate. These leakage current values of Table.1 [2] and used for future calculations of overall leakage currents of test circuits.

Table.1 presents worst case leakage for 11 combination and best leakage for 00 combination which is the minimum leakage vector for two input NAND gate. Chen. et al introduced genetic algorithm for searching MLV with accurate leakage current model [3]. Xiaoying Zhao et al [4] also used genetic algorithm to solve MLV problem with circuit status difference (CSD) as fitness function to overcome the problems from the proposed technique of [3].

The same CSD as fitness function along with genetic algorithm to find optimal solution. The algorithm is implemented in Verilog HDL unlike with 'C' language as in [4]. HDL implementation of the algorithm converges in less time towards best solution. In this paper by using Verilog HDL implementation of genetic algorithm, an innovative attempt is made and succeeded to find optimal solution in fewer number of iterations compared to random search method. It is also reduces the runtime with leakage power reduction. The paper is organized as follows. Brief description of genetic algorithm is given in Section II provides the motivation of this paper and section III and Section IV provides the explanations about genetic algorithm and fitness function. Section V deals with simulation results and analysis of circuits designed. Finally, section VI concludes the paper and section VII defines about future scope of this paper.

Table 1: Leakage Currents For Two Input Nand Gate

Input Vector	Power Dissp. (W)	Leakage current(nA)
00	2.42E-12	37.84 (best)
01	2.61E-11	100.30
10	2.15E-11	95.17
11	3.09E-11	454.5(worst)

2. MOTIVATION

IVC utilizes the stacking effect of the circuit where more number off transistor in series reduced the leakage. In logic circuit leakage is directly describing by means of the input of the gate. It means among all possible combination some input values offer less leakage than other. Table1 describes the leakage power dissipation of NAND logic. Data obtained by simulation in Synopsys HSPICE using the 180 nm TSMC model at 1.8V supply voltage. This is seen from Table 1, changing a logic gate in its minimum leakage vector (00 as in the case of NAND logic) can reduces leakage by on 92.2% of the Worst Leakage State WLS (i.e. 11 as in the case of NAND logic). Implementation using HSPICE and other tools taken a more number of iterations to converge and larger runtime. But implementation of genetic algorithm using verilog HDL providing better result. In combinational circuit every logic gates are directly or not directly depends on the output of the previous logic gate input. It is concluded that an exhaustive approach is

required to locate a minimum leakage vector for a particular circuit while compared to all of its possible input combinations.

Steps for finding MLV

Consider node and link as a transistor and an interconnection respectively.

- i) Select primary input from its primary value to final value or a threshold value.
- ii) Ensure for the transistor which is in OFF states in every path of the graph at a given input.
- iii) If above than one transistor having OFF state in a path around no leakage takes place.
- iv) This process counts the number of OFF transistor in a circuit at every input sample. And a pattern which gives the minimum leakage set as a MLV.
- v) Calculate leakage of the circuit.

3. GENETIC ALGORITHM TO FIND MLV

Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) are population dependent heuristic optimization algorithms that use biologically stimulated mechanisms. Best fitness value is the optimum solution after iterating through number of generation ns [11]. Genetic algorithm is a subclass of evolutionary algorithms inspired by the biological process of genetics and evolution by creating the population of chromosomes. The algorithm starts with the initial population represented by set of chromosomes. Fitness is evaluated for each chromosome in the population. Off springs can be generated by different process steps like selection, cross over and mutation. Off springs with best fitness values will survive to form future generations. When stopping criteria is satisfied for the given number of iterations, algorithm gives the optimum solution. Genetic Algorithm (GA) has the advantage of exploiting historical information to consider on new search points with expected better performance. It derives its behaviour from a metaphor of normal selection and natural genetics by the formation of a population of chromosomes.

The pseudo code of our GA is given as follows.

```
GA ()
{
chromosome_length=length of primary inputs pop size=100; pc =0.96; pm =0.16; generation=1;
initialize a population of the chromosomes while
CSD reduction between ten generations > 0 do
{
evaluate every chromosome in the population roulette wheel selection to select parents crossover and
mutation to form children produce a new generation of the children
}
generation++
}
```


Fig. 2. Flowchart of Genetic Algorithm

The GA used in this paper is tended to locate an input vector which can result in a minimal CSD for a given circuit. Each chromosome is represented with an input vector of the particular circuit. Selection is the process of selecting chromosomes that will make it to the crossover stage. In this paper roulette wheel technique is used in which the parent chromosomes are selected by means of the probabilities proportional to their fitness. Off springs can be generated from selected parent ts in a number of ways in cross over. Single point, two point and uniform crossovers are the different types of crossover mechanisms. Single point cross mover is used and is followed by a mutation in the algorithm.

Fig.3. Single Point Crossover Operator

Crossover is the process of comprising the genes of one chromosome with those of another to create offspring that inherit behaviour of both parents (As shown in Figure 3).

Mutation is the process of shifting bits from one to zero or zero to one in the population. Mutation rate is considered in the paper as 0.01. In this paper, CSD is used as fitness function, which will be introduced afterwards. The GA will be terminated when CSD not reduced between 10 generations.

4. CIRCUIT STATUS DIFFERENCE (CSD) AS FITNESS FUNCTION

CIRCUIT STATUS DIFFERENCE (CSD) [4] is the metric used to determine which input will give minimum leakage current. CSD is considered as fitness function in the paper. It is calculated as the sum of the products of number of transistors in a gate with its hamming distance. Hamming distance is the number of bits with which the given vector is differed from its ideal vector.

Some related definitions:

Input state of a cell: For an n-input cell c_i in a circuit C, a state s is an n-bit number, with every bit representing the respective input bit (0 or 1) to the cell. The set of all possible states is represented as S_i for cell c_i .

Ideal input state of a cell: For an n-input cell type c_i , its ideal state $s_{ideal(i)} \in S_i$ is the one that results in the minimum leakage power of c_i .

Ideal status of a circuit: When all the cells of the circuit are in their ideal input states, it is supposed that the circuit was in an ideal status. However, in reality, this ideal status often does not survive because of the conflicting requirements of cells' inputs. Thus our effort would be to find an near to the ideal circuit status for maximum leakage power reduction.

Circuit status difference: For a input vector $v_i \in V$, the CSD of v_i is defined as

$$CSD(v_i) = \sum \text{weight}(c_i) \cdot HD(s_i, s_{ideal(i)}) \quad \text{---(1)}$$

where $HD(s_i, s_{ideal(i)})$ is the hamming distance among s_i and $s_{ideal(i)}$ for standard cell $c_i \in C$. Intuitively, the leakage power of a cell is relative to its number of transistors in the cell. The significance has an additional advantage that it does not change by process technology.

The CSD shows the likelihood of a circuit status under input vector v_i and the ideal circuit status. The lesser the CSD is, the more likely the circuit status under input v_i will be to its ideal status.

5. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The circuits of INVERTER, NAND2 AND NAND3 were simulated using both cadence and Verilog HDL. The Leakage current and runtime implementation of INVERTER, NAND2 and NAND3 were shown in the Table.3 to Table.5.

Table.3. Leakage current and runtime for INVERTER

INPUT	Runtime in HDL (sec)	Runtime in cadence (sec)	Leakage (nA)
0	0.56	1.03	best:100.3
1			worst:227.2

Table.4. Leakage current and runtime for NAND2

INPUT	Runtime in HDL (sec)	Runtime in cadence (sec)	Leakage (nA)
00	0.62	1.09	best: 37.84
01			2nd worst: 100.30
10			95.17
11			worst: 454.5

Table.5. Leakagecurrent and runtime for NAND3

INPUT	Runtime in HDL (sec)	Runtime in cadence (sec)	Leakage(nA)
000	0.78	1.15	best: 22.84
001			37.84
010			37.84
011			2ndworst: 100.30
100			37.01
101			95.17
110			94.87
111			worst: 852.40

The algorithm is applied to four,six and eight input NAND-NAND test circuits to find MLV, leakage current and the number of iterations of the corresponding circuits.

Fig. 4. Four Input NAND-NAND Test Circuit

Figure.4 shows four input NAND-NAND test circuit. As an example Table.2 presented in the paper with circuit status difference values of figure.4, for all the sixteen possible combinations. The table indicates least value of CSD for “0000” combination among all the test inputs. This “0000” input is the MLV for the four input circuit given in figure.4. With the genetic algorithm implementation of figure 4, same vector is obtained as a best solution which is given with least CSD value from Table.2.

Table.2.Circuit Status Difference Values of Figure.4

S.No	Input Vector	CSD
1	0000	8
2	0001	12
3	0010	12
4	0011	12
5	0100	12
6	0101	16
7	0110	16
8	0111	16
9	1000	12

10	1001	16
11	1010	16
12	1011	16
13	1100	12
14	1101	16
15	1110	16
16	1111	16

Fig.5. Six input NAND-NAND test circuit

Fig.6. Eight input NAND-NAND test circuit

The Figures 5 and 6 are the six and eight input NANAD-NAND test circuits. The MLV, Leakage current and number of iterations for the corresponding circuits are shown in table 6.

Table.6. Minimum leakage vectors for test circuits

Test circuit	MLV	Leakage current (nA)	No.of iterations
4 input NAND NAND circuit	0000	115.52	10
6 input circuit	0000	229.65	20
8 input circuit	0000	278.04	95

Table.6 shows minimum leakage vectors and leakage currents for various test circuits along with number of iterations. All test circuits can be forced to MLV during standby mode to have minimum leakage current. These MLVs are obtained from genetic algorithm. HDL implementation of algorithm takes less number of iterations compared to random methods to give optimum solution. Genetic algorithm with HDL implementation converges faster as it takes less number of iterations with runtime saving.

Genetic algorithm is implemented in Verilog HDL to find minimum leakage state of the combinational test circuit. Simulation and synthesis is carried out using Xilinx tool with ISE 9.2i version. Test circuits can be parked with the respective minimum leakage state during standby mode to reduce leakage power. This improves backup time of any mobile operated device, which operates most of the time in sleep state or standby mode.

Fig.7.C17 Benchmark Circuit

The C17 benchmark circuit has been taken for the analysis. The C17 benchmark circuit is shown in the figure 7. The Table.7 presents analysis for ISCAS85 benchmark circuit C17 in terms of leakage current, number of iterations and runtime savings.

Table.7. Comparison of runtime with abdoul rjoub et al

Test circuit	MLV	Leakage current (nA)	No.of iterations	Run time for HDL (Sec)	Run time random search method (Sec)
C17 Benchmark circuit	01000	229.32	10	1.26	2.56

The table 7 shows the comparison results of proposed implementation with Abdoul et al. Columns 2 and 3 in table 7 gives minimum leakage vector and leakage current. Column 4 shows number of iterations taken by the algorithm to search for minimum leakage state. Column 5 presents runtime for the genetic algorithm to obtain best solution. Column 6 is the runtime taken by random search method[4]. Comparison results of columns 5 and 6 shows that HDL implementation of genetic algorithm gives best solution in less number of iterations with runtime savings.

The genetic algorithm implementation with HDL can be used in input vector control approach for fast searching of best vector and leakage control reduction. This implementation can be combined with fast input vector control algorithms and gate replacement algorithm in to obtain better leakage reductions.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a new implementation of heuristic algorithm to search for minimum leakage vector. Verilog implementation of Genetic algorithm to find MLV is presented in this paper. An innovative attempt is made with HDL implementation of the algorithm and succeeded to find optimal solution in less number of iterations. From the simulation results, concluded that algorithm converges to best solution with runtime savings compared to random search method. Test circuit can be applied with minimum leakage vector to reduce the leakage during sleep mode.

7. FUTURE SCOPE

In future the concept of Input Vector Control approach will be combined with Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) for the fast generation of test sequences. The LFSR randomly generates the test patterns for corresponding test circuits. This will increase the speed of operation as well as reduces the total area required, memory size. This furthermore reduces the power consumption, running time of operation and

number of iterations. This implementation can be combined with other algorithms like fast input vector control and gate replacement to obtain better leakage reductions.

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